

Source: Karbalaie, S., Golieskardi, A., Watt, D. U., Boiret, M., [Hanachi P.](#), Walker, T. R., & Karami, A. (2020). Analysis and inorganic composition of microplastics in commercial Malaysian fish meals. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 150. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2019.110687>

Analysis and inorganic composition of microplastics in commercial Malaysian fish meals

Samaneh Karbalaie¹, Abolfazl Golieskardi², Dorothy Uning Watt³, Mathieu Boiret⁴, [Parichehr Hanachi](#)¹, Tony R. Walkere⁵, Ali Karamif⁶

¹ Department of Biotechnology, Faculty of Biological Science, Alzahra University, Tehran, Iran

² Department of Quality Assurance, Kian Fara Pars Pharmaceutical Co, 4818179419, Sari, Iran

³ Laboratory of Aquatic Toxicology, Department of Environmental and Occupational Health, Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, Universiti Putra Malaysia, 43400, Selangor, Malaysia

⁴ Horiba Scientific, Avenue de La Vauve, Passage Jobin Yvon, 91120, Palaiseau, France

⁵ School for Resource and Environmental Studies, Dalhousie University, Halifax, NS, B3H 4R2, Canada

⁶ Environmental Futures Research Institute, Griffith University, Brisbane, QLD, 4111, Australia

Abstract

Presence of microplastics (MPs) in a broad range of wild and cultured marine organisms is well-documented, but transfer mechanisms by which cultured organisms are contaminated with MPs is poorly understood. MP loads in three Malaysian commercial brands of fish meal were investigated. Chemical composition of extracted MP-like particles was confirmed using micro-Raman spectroscopy. Inorganic composition of MPs and pigment particles were assessed through energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX). Out of 336 extracted particles, 64.3% were plastic polymers, 25% pigment particles, 4.2% non-plastic items, and 6.5% were unidentified. Fragments were the dominant form of MPs (78.2%) followed by filaments (13.4%) and films (8.4%). This study demonstrates that cultured organisms could be exposed to high levels of MPs via MP contaminated fish/shellfish used in fish meal production. Fish meal replacement with other sources of protein including meat meals and plant-based meals may mitigate MP exposure to cultured or farmed organisms.

Keywords: Microplastics (MPs), Fish meal, Cultured or farmed organisms, Isolation, Raman spectroscopy.